

The health and social care of people living with diagnosed or suspected dementia in prison: Final Lay Report

UNIVERSITY OF THE
WEST of SCOTLAND
UWS

Alzheimer
Scotland Centre
for Policy and
Practice

*This work is supported by
The Dunhill Medical Trust
(Grant number RPGF/2006\236)*

 Remarkable research
for healthy ageing
THE DUNHILL MEDICAL TRUST

Summary

Introduction

Prisoners with a suspected or diagnosed dementia are becoming an increasing concern for prison services and prison healthcare staff due to the complexity of their health and social care needs.

The number of prisoners over 60 years of age has trebled in UK prisons between 2002 and 2016. Recent data from England suggested that **7.2% of those aged over 50 years in prison had dementia**. This is much higher than would be found in community populations of the same age. There is very little known about this vulnerable population or how they are cared for in Scotland.

Methods

This multi method qualitative study aimed to identify and develop new and effective ways to improve the health and well-being of the increasing numbers of older people living with a diagnosed or suspected dementia in prison.

Twenty semi structured interviews were completed with staff across four prisons in Scotland that housed the largest number of men over 65 years of age. Five interviews were completed with men identified as having a diagnosed or suspected dementia and four staff involved in their care and support. In addition health information from the five men's healthcare records was collected.

Three stakeholder workshops were held to co-produce a model and evidenced informed care pathway for people living with a diagnosed or suspected dementia living in Scottish prisons. Two stakeholder workshops co-designed the model and pathway to ensure they were accessible and attractive to use.

Results

At the time of data collection most of the prisoners known to have a dementia diagnosis or suspected dementia had complex health and social care needs, and some were living with advanced dementia.

Prison healthcare staff reported taking a 'case by case' approach to their pre-and post-diagnostic care. Meeting these prisoner's needs was complicated by the absence of organisational leads for care of older adults or people with dementia and there was no pathway or model in place to guide staff.

Furthermore, prison healthcare teams often had difficulty accessing specialist community services, including old age psychiatry, and staff such as Occupational Therapists to support social and recreational participation and the implementation of reasonable adjustments.

There was a lack of dementia education and knowledge about how to provide pre and post diagnostic dementia care in this setting amongst staff.

Conclusions and Recommendations

The absence of clear leadership, limited resource to support dementia capabilities and care and difficulties accessing specialist services compounds vulnerabilities and care inequalities for those with a dementia diagnosis or suspected dementia living in Scottish prisons.

Consideration should be given to identifying organisational leads across NHS prison healthcare, the Scottish Prison Service and Health and Social Care partnerships for those with a diagnosed or suspected dementia in prisons. The capability and capacity of prison and prison healthcare staff and their access to specialist services needs to improve if the dementia related and palliative care needs of men living in prison are to be met.

The findings arising from this research have informed the co-production of two important evidence informed innovations namely a Model of Care and a Care Pathway. These could serve as tools for change that would enable the right care, at the right time, by the right people, and provide an opportunity to assess risk and plan care for the future.

About the final lay report

This is the fifth in a series of five reports. This lay report brings together the entire study, outlining the main findings and the co-design process and outputs before presenting the recommendations arising from the study.

The other reports from the study can be found below:

1. Health and social care provision to people living with a diagnosed or suspected dementia living in four Scottish prisons: **Phase 1 Report**
2. Case studies of people with a diagnosed or suspected dementia living in prison: **Phase 2 Report**
3. Co-designed evidenced informed healthcare pathways for people living with a diagnosed or suspected dementia living in Scottish prisons: **Phase 3 Report**
4. The health and social care of people living with diagnosed or suspected dementia in prison: **Final Project Report**

Background

Prisoners with a suspected or diagnosed dementia are becoming an increasing concern prison services and prison healthcare staff due to the complexity of their health and social care needs. There is very little known about this population or how they are cared for in Scotland.

The number of those over 60 years trebled in UK prisons between 2002 and 2016. A recent English study suggested a much higher prevalence of dementia in prisons than found among community populations of the same age (Forsyth et al., 2020).

7.2% It suggested 7.2% of those aged over 50 years in prison had dementia.

The Scottish Prison Service considers those 55 years and older to be older prisoners. Improved ways of recognising and managing the increasing number of older prisoners with complex health needs including dementia is urgent. The consequences of not doing so may heighten fear and distress, reduce opportunities to access appropriate healthcare interventions and support, and violate human rights.

Study Methods

The study had three phases.

Phase 1:

To describe the current referral, diagnostic and post-diagnostic healthcare pathways and understand how later life well-being was promoted and health risks reduced we conducted 20 semi-structured interviews with a range of staff working in the four prisons in Scotland that house the highest number of men over 65 years.

Phase 2:

To explore the dementia lived and care experience we conducted five semi-structured interviews with men identified by prison healthcare teams as having a suspected or diagnosed dementia. We also interviewed four staff involved in their care and support. The men consented that the prison healthcare staff provided us with information about their health histories from their healthcare records.

Phase 3:

To co-design pre and post-diagnostic healthcare pathway and model we held five workshops involving 38 stakeholders. Stakeholders included a range of prison health care staff, prison staff, staff from community criminal justice and dementia organisations, people with lived experience of dementia and family carers.

Summary Findings from phase 1 and 2

Identifying people with a suspected dementia

There was no standardised way of identifying people with a suspected dementia within and across the four prisons. The national screening programme for prisons in Scotland does not currently include cognitive screening for older prisoners. Our findings suggested that prison healthcare staff were reliant on those living in or working more closely with prisoners alerting them to concerns.

“Sometimes we have very little contact, if they aren't on supervised medications, we might never meet them. It's a health centre within a prison, it's not that we're nurses on the halls providing care. It is very much we're here for treatment rooms, emergencies and dispensing meds. So, we don't have a lot of input up on the halls. The community carers, they bring a lot of stuff to our attention, because they spend the majority of time with these guys. And the SPS staff. So they would all be part of identifying it”.

Prison 3: Primary Care Nurse 1

If a person was brought to the attention of the prison healthcare team, the mental health nurses carried out an initial cognitive screen and history taking in consultation with a sessional forensic psychiatrist or GP.

Assessing people for dementia

The staff reported that assessing a person for dementia was often complex due to several intersecting issues related to the poor health of prison population, a lack of clarity around the processes of referral and assessment and the nature of and resources afforded to providing healthcare in a prison setting.

The case studies illustrated the poor health so often attributed to the prison population generally and more specifically older prisoners.

- The age range of the men was 60-79 years
- Four were over 65 years
- All were on long term sentences (over four years)
- All had multiple co-morbidities, this ranged from 3-8, all were prescribed multiple medications, this ranged from 4-11
- Two of the men were in receipt of personal care provided by external carers contracted by the prison service. This meant they had been assessed by the nursing team as requiring support to meet their fundamental care needs such as washing, dressing etc.
- Three has significant mobility issues and either used a walking frame and or wheelchair to mobilise
- Two were accommodated in accessible cells
- One had an airbed
- Four of the five men could not participate in work programmes, needed assistance if they wanted to go outside or visit the library. They largely stayed in their cell or the immediate area, relied on their cellmates or one or two other prisoners to remind them or help them with ordering, cleaning their cell, or occasionally going
- For these four men their greatest concern was around their deteriorating physical health and for two of them it was about maintaining contact with family members

"I fall about, because I'm... I've no balance, and I keep telling them, I keep telling them and saying, "Look, I've no balance at all," ken? "Oh right, right (name of person)." But nothing gets done. Honestly, and it's so irritating. It's difficult for me to move about myself, you know? That's terrible. I'm using that, this walker here, mainly. Well I'm... well it's quite difficult, especially in the cell because there's obstacles, you know? And you have to hang onto the sinks and hang onto the back of chairs and everything. I mean, I'm just... I'm no' doing well in my cell!"

Fraser: Case study 3

None of the staff were aware of the NHS dementia education resources freely available to all health and social care staff. All staff felt they did not have the appropriate skills, knowledge and expertise in dementia. This feeling was heightened by having no formal pre and post diagnosis care pathway in place to guide the screening, assessment and referral process and staff roles within it. A 'case by case approach' was adopted. .

"We're not experienced in the area, we can only do it when something occurs, like 'oh hang on a minute, we have to modify this or put this in place.' So we're learning, and when you're dealing with people, you shouldn't be learning, we should have things in place for them. But we can't plan for every eventuality, we can only do what we can. So yeah, there's multiple complexities and we absolutely struggle and need more help in these areas".

Prison 4: Mental Health Nurse 2

Workforce shortages, particularly amongst mental health nurses and limited availability of sessional staff meant assessment processes could be lengthy and disjointed. Our case studies illustrated that four of the five men were undergoing assessment for suspected dementia, the duration of the assessment period at the time of interview varied from one month to 4 years. Only one man had a confirmed clinical diagnosis of dementia

The point in the assessment process that the four prison healthcare teams referred to old age psychiatry varied as did the support they received from old age psychiatry services in different Health boards. For example, one community old age psychiatry service had declined a referral put in by the prison healthcare team on the grounds that they did not provide a service to people in prison.

"I've gone through cycles of challenging the referral process. I did a standard referral through Old Age Psychiatry in the same manner I did only a few months earlier in the community for a similar gentleman. My community gentleman ended up being assessed, whereas my patient in prison within twenty-four hours, an e-mail following a telephone call to the health centre, came through: "We just don't see patients in prison." These should be referred to the forensic psychiatrists. In a prison health care setting, a lot of our patients have mental health issues and don't have access to psychiatry as much as they should. People with a specialty should be working with a client and diagnosing it. Just as if somebody needed a cardiologist, they need a cardiologist. So that was disappointing though very unsurprising to me. But that case was a classic example of a referral that didn't deviant in one way from a similar referral in the community with two separate outcomes"

Prison 1: GP2

Whereas another prison healthcare team reported at the end of phase 2, they had a newly established an assessment and referral pathway with their local old age psychiatry team in place. This disparity perhaps illustrates the national variation in practice amongst memory clinics, which provide clinical assessment for individuals with cognitive complaints or suspected neurodegenerative disease. They were found to have no standardised approach to the assessment of individuals and variation in the implementation of assessment and care pathways (SIGN 168, 2023). Although the views varied as to when old age psychiatry should become involved in the assessment process there was widespread agreement amongst prison healthcare teams that specialist input was required to support diagnosis.

The process for referring those with a suspected cognitive impairment who were under 65 years remained unclear in all four prison healthcare teams. The different age thresholds applied in prison (55 years) and in the NHS (65 years) creates a potential challenge when it comes to those in prison accessing NHS services. The need for prison healthcare teams to refer to other NHS community services was common, as specialist services such as occupational therapy (for people aged over 65 years), physiotherapy, speech and language therapy and audiology were not available within the prisons that participated in this study.

"It would be myself that would refer them for OT or PT, sight, hearing, speech and language, any of those if it's necessary, I'll have to refer them onto the hospital. And the social care assistant, I think, SPS. The nurses can list them for the optician, but the rest I have to refer them on. I have to refer them out for OT, nothing on site in this prison, there's not even physio on site here. But the optician's come in. I try and get the team involved and make sure that the medication becomes supervised. And let the SPS know".

Prison 1: Mental Health Nurse

Working with people with dementia

Prison healthcare teams reported that community teams responded to requests, although wait times could be lengthy. The wait times had lengthened as a result of COVID restrictions, this had also affected the availability and ability of sessional support staff to come into the prison healthcare centres. The prison healthcare staff also reported that getting supports in place for things such as modified diet, mobility aids etc. could take a long time due to a combination of getting access to some supports and complexity of organising those supports within a prison regime.

"But again, it is – because of the limitations of the environment... so something that would be quite simple somewhere else, for instance arranging an appropriate diet... so the kitchen will take instruction from the nutritionist, who doesn't come into the prison, who will only give advice, but doesn't come in to assess people, and is reliant on our assessment. So there are assessments that we can do, but she will ask for a MUST, which we are not all familiar with. And then the kitchen can respond with a modified diet. We do have a speech and language therapist who can assess swallowing and things like that. But it takes a prolonged period of time, and we have anticipatory care plans in place. But again, it's the way that these are communicated. And having a cohesive plan that involves all the team, and all the team that can contribute to, to support the person."

Mental Health Nurse: Case study 4 and 5

Personal care was provided by external carers contracted by SPS. If there was a shortage or high turnover of nursing staff, there could be delays in updating personal care plans which are important for ensuring the consistency and coordination of care. There were very few accessible cells. Common adaptations were hospital beds, grab rails, commodes, and high back chairs. Normal cells tended not to be adapted.

"Modified accommodation... we're very limited. Signage, we do have a couple of guys who we put coloured tape round their door, so they can identify it. We have one of the patients with the dementia, we changed the colour of the paint. Other changes, we would provide some equipment. Things like non-slip surface material, the surfaces in their cell are quite light, so we got a dark blue colour so we could sit their plates and things on it, so they could identify it, because they were struggling to see it. We put in grab rails".

Prison 3: Carer 1

The prison healthcare staff were aware that psychosocial activities and supports to promote health and well-being available to many people living with dementia in the community were not available to those in prison. None of the staff were aware of Scottish Government Local Delivery Plan standard on post diagnostic support (PDS) or the PDS models used to inform this work in the community.

All four prison healthcare teams operated monthly multidisciplinary healthcare team meetings. Though not all operated interagency healthcare meetings that involved prison staff for people 'of concern.' All the staff felt this kind of meeting supported communication and interagency working.

Prison staff tried to adapt regimes (if COVID restrictions and staffing allowed) to allow people who became distressed when locked in their cell out to walk about during periods where other people may be locked up. However, prison officers were there primarily to manage risk and safety and there were reports that occasionally people with dementia, who were very agitated, and perceived as a threat to the health and safety of staff were restrained.

People leaving prison encounter many difficulties accessing a range of supports such as housing, benefits and GP registration, this is likely to be exacerbated for those with limited mobility, mental illness, and a disability (Scottish Government, 2021). On liberation people may not be going back to the area they lived in previously or may not know where they are going to stay until the day of liberation. Registration with a GP prior to liberation was not possible. If a person had been in prison less than 3 months they could go back to their own GP, otherwise they needed to apply to register with a GP who would then be allocated to them, this process could take days or weeks.

So we're hamstrung by the fact that we can't register with GPs before they're liberated, so we can't do a good hand over of care. We can just invite the GP to get a mandate, to get in touch with us, or to give recommendations on the discharge letter, and hope that the patient retains it, and gives it to the new GP. Because if they've got a determinate sentence, they've got no follow-up if they choose not to have voluntary through-care. And we can't involve their relatives, because often their relatives don't want anything to do with them, and because of confidentiality. We can't pass it on.

Prison 3: Mental Health Nurse

When people's dementia advanced to point that they had very significant, sometimes round the clock healthcare needs and were routinely becoming distressed, the prison healthcare teams began looking for alternative accommodation.

"I know guys that are on like end of life care and stuff, they can get transferred out to hospital or hospices, I don't know what the process would be for someone with like end of life like kind of last stages of dementia. So it's difficult because we can't transfer out for psychiatry".

Prison 1: Mental Health Nurse

None of the men from the case studies were due to be released in the next few months, though it was a concern for one man felt who felt he would need to be placed in a care home on release. Finding suitable accommodation and assessing the risk to the public of a person with dementia that was due for release or required to be transferred was fraught with difficulty and complexity.

The co-design process and outputs: phase 3

We held three in person stakeholder workshops involving thirty-eight people in early 2023. The aims of the workshops were to:

- Co-design evidence informed referral, diagnostic and post diagnostic healthcare pathway and stakeholders
- Co-produce an evidence informed model for promoting later life wellbeing, and managing risks

During the workshops, the research team presented the high-level findings, themes from the data and two case study vignettes. The workshops facilitated participants to consider how the five objectives listed below could be achieved.

1. Develop a process for identifying and assessing prisoners with suspected cognitive impairment or dementia.
2. Develop a diagnostic pathway that includes input from specialist community services.
3. Develop multidisciplinary care planning to address individual physical and mental and care needs.
4. Develop multidisciplinary care planning to address individuals needs for reasonable adjustments, and participation in social and recreational activities.
5. Develop multidisciplinary care planning to prepare and support individuals for progression and release.

The desired actions that were strongly articulated included:

- ➔ Consider introducing tailored cognitive screening for older people in prison.
- ➔ Develop and implement a care pathway.
- ➔ Routinely get consent to share early to streamline the sharing of information.
- ➔ Record cognitive impairment in both NHS and SPS information systems.
- ➔ All Staff GDPR and information sharing training.
- ➔ All staff dementia training and education.
- ➔ Introduce NHS, SPS and Local authority adult services or HSCP lead that has responsibility for older adults/people with cognitive impairment in prison.
- ➔ On diagnosis a named person should be allocated to support integrated care management.
- ➔ An Integrated Case management (ICM) would focus on care and risk.
- ➔ Prison healthcare teams need better access to a variety of specialist community services such as old age psychiatry, staff with knowledge and skills to support social and recreational participation and identify required reasonable adjustments.
- ➔ Improved interagency working and communication.
- ➔ People living in prison with dementia need to be identified in government strategies.
- ➔ Build design of new prisons needs to take account of ageing population and there needs to be investment to retrofit and increase number of accessible cells.

Model and care pathway

Taking account of the evidence from this study, a recent English study (Forsyth et al 2020) and the priorities agreed in the stakeholder workshops we drafted a model and care pathway.

Workshop participants reviewed and provided comments on successive drafts of the model and care pathway. Both the model and pathway are underpinned by the [HMIPs Inspecting and Monitoring: Standard 9: Health and Wellbeing](#) and the [National Health and Social Care Standards](#). Both adopt a human rights based and person-centred approach to care and treatment. The model and pathway sit within the recent recommendations made by the Mental Welfare Commission (2022) and the reports commissioned by the Scottish Government into the health and social care needs of prisoners (2021 and 2022).

The overarching aim of this model (Figure 1) is to represent the care principles to ensure the well-being of people with suspected or diagnosed dementia in prison and on release. It illustrates what needs to be in place to ensure an individual receives the right care, at the right time, in the right place, from the right people – those with the values, knowledge and skills to provide safe high-quality care and support.

Figure 1:
Model

HMIPs Inspecting and Monitoring: Standard 9: Health and Wellbeing
 National Health and Social Care Standards: My support, My life
 Assessment, diagnosis, care and support for people with dementia and their carers (sign.ac.uk)

Figure 2: Care pathway (overleaf) illustrates how identification, assessment, diagnosis, post diagnostic care and support for people with a suspected or diagnosed cognitive impairment or dementia can be operationalised and achieved. It is acknowledged that routine cognitive screening currently does not happen and would require planning and resource to incorporate it into current health assessment processes, be they those conducted post admission or annually.

This care pathway is not a standard or a guideline. It is a flexible resource that can be used to support the implementation of current standards such as the [HMIPs Inspecting and Monitoring: Standard 9: Health and Wellbeing](#), the [National Health and Social Care Standards: My support, My life](#) which adopt a human rights based approach. It recognises the need for all staff to be educated and supported to fulfil their role in preventing harm associated with prison life and promoting the health and wellbeing of all prisoners. See [SIGN 168](#) for clinical guidance on the assessment, diagnosis, care and support for people living with dementia.

Co-design workshops

To ensure the model, pathway and other resources were accessible and attractive to those who would use them we invited all the workshop participants to attend two online sessions to co-design the resources with our creative communication agency Electrify.

The model and pathway are part of a suite of resources designed to support those involved in the delivery of health, social care and support to people living with a suspected or diagnosed cognitive impairment or dementia in prison. The resources are hosted on a microsite, which can be found on several organisational and network websites.

dementiainprisons.com

dementiainprisons.com

Figure 2:
Care pathway

*The Montreal Cognitive Assessment (MoCA) is considered better than the MMSE as a global assessment tool (Roalf et al. 2013). It takes 10 minutes to complete. [Free one-hour online training with certification](#) for publicly operated health institutions.

*The ACE-III is a robust tool, often used in specialised assessments to assess for dementia and other neurological disorders. It takes 15-30 minutes to administer. [Free online training for NHS staff](#). Score of ≤82 indicates possible dementia, score of 83-88 possible cognitive impairment and need for specialist assessment.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are intended to propel policy and practice actions that will improve the health and care of people living with a suspected and diagnosed dementia in prison.

Our recommendations sit within the context of the recent reports and recommendations made by the Mental Welfare Commission (2022) and the reports commissioned by the Scottish Government into the health and social care needs of prisoners (2021 and 2022). Together these reports highlight many similar strategic and operational issues concerning how the resource currently afforded to prison health care struggles to meet the complex physical and mental health needs of the populations they serve.

Our recommendations shine a light on the actions and changes that are required to support an increasing number of people living with a suspected or diagnosed dementia in prison.

High level recommendations

Implement a whole system model of care, one that is integrated, multidisciplinary and inclusive of the person and their family, with the persons biopsychosocial-spiritual well-being at its centre.

We found that there was no model of care or care pathway in place for prison and prison healthcare staff to support them to provided pre and post diagnostic care for people with a suspected or diagnosed dementia, many of whom had complex health and social care needs. We found that a 'case by case' approach was adopted.

Prison healthcare teams had difficulty accessing specialist community services such as old age psychiatry, and those that would support social and recreational participation and the reasonable adjustments a person needed. Developments in dementia care such as the use of relationship or person-centred care planning and post diagnostic support were not in evidence.

Dementia education should be mandatory for all staff, so they are equipped with the knowledge and skills to respond appropriately to those with suspected or diagnosed dementia.

There was no evidence of staff being aware of or supported to use the Promoting Excellence dementia education resources that are freely available to all health and social care staff. Very few staff had any dementia education or training that enabled them to feel competent or confident in responding appropriately or providing care to people with a suspected or diagnosed dementia.

Agency leads for NHS prison healthcare, Scottish Prison Service and the Health and Social Care partnership / social work should be identified to lead on improving the pre and post diagnostic care for those with suspected and diagnosed dementia and staff education.

The SPS and NHS had no appointed leads for older people or people with suspected or diagnosed dementia in prison. Staff felt that due to their age and or their disability this group of people could fall under the equality and diversity remit and there should be designated NHS, SPS and SW/HSCP agency leads who could support multi agency working within and at the interface of prison.

It was felt that strong interagency leadership was one way to support improvements in pre and post diagnostic care and staff education.

Operational recommendations

1. Consideration should be given to resourcing the introduction of brief cognitive screening for those who are sentenced and 55 years and over.
2. Prison healthcare staff administering cognitive screening should be supported to undertake the free online training.
3. Prison and NHS staff should work in partnership to support consent to share being sought early to streamline the sharing of information within and between prison, NHS and partner agencies.
4. Education about ageing and dementia should be mandatory. Prison and prison healthcare staff should be supported to use the dementia education resources in the NHS for Education Promoting Excellence Dementia Knowledge and Skills framework appropriate to their role.
5. The evidence-informed co-produced care pathway should be made available to all staff working in and at the interface of prison to guide the processes for cognitive screening, referral, assessment and post diagnostic care.
6. Prison healthcare leads should work in partnership with specialist services to develop a diagnostic pathway for accessing an old age psychiatry and other appropriate specialist services for those under 65 years for those with a suspected dementia.
7. Those with a suspected or diagnosed dementia should get a formal assessment of their needs carried out by a health, allied health, or social care professional with the appropriate dementia knowledge and skills.
8. Those diagnosed with dementia should have an integrated person-centred package of care inclusive of the person and their family to meet their biopsychosocial-spiritual needs within the prison setting.
9. Support should be given to people to maintain positive contact with families where possible and engagement where possible with families should be sought to support person centred care planning.
10. Consideration should be given to how people with a suspected or diagnosed dementia can access occupational therapy to ensure reasonable adjustments are in place and they have access to appropriate social and recreational activities to promote wellbeing.
11. Consideration should be given to ensuring that those with a suspected or diagnosed dementia have a named point of contact, professional or case manager who is a health or social care professional with the appropriate knowledge, skills and expertise in dementia.
12. Prison and prison healthcare leads should consider working in partnership to ensure interagency healthcare meetings are in place and individuals with suspected or diagnosed dementia are discussed and reviewed.
13. Prison and prison healthcare leads should work in partnership to give early consideration of more appropriate accommodation for those whose advanced dementia care needs cannot be met within the prison setting.

References

Forsyth K, Heathcote L, Senior J et al., Dementia and mild MCI in prisoners aged over 50 years in England and Wales: a mixed-methods study. Health Services and Delivery Research, Vol 8, Issue 27. 2020 ISSN 2050-4349

Health and Social Care Standards: my support, my life. <https://www.gov.scot/publications/health-social-care-standards-support-life/>

HMIPs Inspecting and Monitoring: Standard 9: [Health and Wellbeing](https://www.prisoninspectorscotland.gov.uk/publications/inspecting-and-monitoring-standard-9-health-and-wellbeing) <https://www.prisoninspectorscotland.gov.uk/publications/inspecting-and-monitoring-standard-9-health-and-wellbeing>

House of Commons Justice Committee Ageing prison population. [Fifth Report of Session 2019–21 Ageing prison population \(parliament.uk\)](https://www.parliament.uk/publications/54404)

Mental Welfare Commission (2022). Mental health support in Scotland's prisons: under-served and under-resourced. <https://www.mwscot.org.uk/sites/default/files/2022-04/PrisonReport-April2022.pdf>

Roalf, D.R et al., (2013) Comparative accuracies of two common screening instruments for classification of Alzheimer's disease, mild MCI, and healthy aging. Alzheimer's & Dementia. doi.org/10.1016/j.jalz.2012.10.001

Scottish Government (2021) Prison population: social care needs. <https://www.gov.scot/publications/understanding-social-care-support-needs-scotlands-prison-population/pages/2/>

Scottish Government (2022) Understanding the physical health care needs of Scotland's prison population. <https://www.gov.scot/publications/understanding-physical-health-care-needs-scotlands-prison-population/pages/4/>

SIGN 168 (2023) [Assessment, diagnosis, care and support for people with dementia and their carers \(sign.ac.uk\)](https://www.sign.ac.uk/sign-168)

Acknowledgements

Many thanks to all the organisations and individuals who enabled this research or participated in the study sharing their experiences and views.

This project was funded by the Dunhill Medical Trust [grant number RPGF/2006\236] and focussed on improving dementia care in prisons through co-designing an evidence informed dementia care pathway and other practical resources for staff working in Scottish prisons. The study commenced in Spring 2021 and reported in early 2024.

Remarkable research
for healthy ageing
THE DUNHILL MEDICAL TRUST

About the Research Team

Dr Rhoda MacRae,
Principal Investigator and
Reader, Alzheimer Centre
for Policy and Practice,
School of Health and Life
Sciences, University of the
West of Scotland

Prof Debbie Tolson,

Co-investigator and Director, Alzheimer Centre for
Policy and Practice, School of Health and Life Sciences,
University of the West of Scotland

Dr James Taylor,

Co-investigator and Head of Division of Health and
Life Sciences, University of the West of Scotland

Dr Kirstin Anderson,

Co-investigator and Lecturer in Criminology,
Edinburgh Napier University

Dr Natalie Chalmers,

Research Associate,
University of Edinburgh

Dr Tom Russ,

External Consultant and Director, Alzheimer Scotland
Dementia Research Centre, University of Edinburgh

Prof Lindsay Thompson, External Consultant and
Medical Director of The State Hospital, University
of Edinburgh

Glossary

Cognitive or Mild cognitive impairment, often known as MCI, describes a set of symptoms, that produce a decline in mental abilities. The difficulties caused by MCI are worse than would normally be expected for a healthy person of the same age. A person with MCI has mild problems with one or more of the following: memory, reasoning, planning or problem-solving, attention, language and visual depth perception. It is estimated that between 5 and 20% of people aged over 65 have MCI. It is not a type of dementia, but a person with MCI is more likely to go on to develop dementia (Alzheimer's Society, 2023).

Dementia is an umbrella term describing a progressive neurodegenerative syndrome caused by illnesses such as Alzheimer's disease that cause structural and chemical changes to the brain. The changes most notably affect memory, orientation, comprehension, calculation, learning capacity, language, and judgement. Consciousness is not affected. The impairment in cognitive function is commonly accompanied, and occasionally preceded, by deterioration in emotional control, social behaviour, or motivation (WHO 2017). As the illness progresses the trajectory is not fixed nor predictable, and people can and do live for months and years with advanced dementia-specific palliative care needs (Reisberg et al 2006) before they reach the stage of dying with dementia.

Montreal Cognitive Assessment (MoCA) is a short cognitive screening tool.

Mini Mental State Examination (MMSE) is a short cognitive screening tool.

6-item cognitive impairment test (6CIT) is a short cognitive screening tool.

Addenbrooke's Cognitive Examination, third revision (ACE)- III, is a more comprehensive cognitive screening tool.

Residential area is the term this report uses for describing the areas in the prison where people in prison were accommodated. The prisons had different names for these areas including hall, wing, unit, flat.

dementiainprisons.com

**Alzheimer
Scotland Centre
for Policy and
Practice**

If referring to or using material from this publication please use the following citation
MacRae, R, Tolson, D, Taylor, J, Anderson, K, Chalmers, N, Russ, R and Thompson, L (2024).
The health and social care of people with a diagnosed or suspected dementia living in
prison: lay report

